

FAIR Reference Group & Working Groups (2025)

To support the implementation of the FAIR strategy, the Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science has established a reference group responsible for national coordination.

The task of the reference group is to follow the national development of the FAIR Strategy. The strategy contains a number of principles and proposed initiatives that help support the implementation of the FAIR principles. The reference group has also established six working groups consisting of experts from private and public institutions.

Members of the FAIR Reference Group 2025		
Name	Position	Institution
Helle Zinner Henriksen (Chair) (from august 2025)	Professor (MSO), chair of DeiC's board	Copenhagen Business School
John Renner Hansen (until august 2025)	Professor	University of Copenhagen
Annemarie Falktoft	Deputy Director	Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science
Anne Sofie Fink Kjeldgaard	Head of data management	DeiC – Danish e- Infrastructure Consortium
Børge Lindberg	Investment Officer	Innovation Fund Denmark
Carsten Sørensen	Head of department, Finance	Copenhagen Business School
Emilie Dupont Skovgaard	Senior consultant	Universities Denmark
Kim Brinckmann	Deputy Director, Research and Innovation	University of Copenhagen
Lasse Aistrup Rosendahl	Director	Aarhus University
Lene Oddershede (Until December 2025)	Senior Vice President	Novo Nordisk Foundation
Martin Svensson	Head of department, Mathematics and Computer Science	University of Southern Denmark
Morten Andreasen	Senior Adviser	Danish National Research Foundation
Søren Broberg Nielsen	Head of function	Aarhus University
Ulla Gro Nielsen	Director, technical sciences	Novo Nordisk Foundation
Hanne-Louise Kirkegaard (Observer)	Senior Consultant	Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science
Tore Burkal Larsen (Observer)	Specialist	Independent Research Fund Denmark

Members of the working groups (2025)

Working group A – Policies, tools and research support for FAIR data management

The working group addresses initiatives requiring national coordination related to the following focus areas of the strategy:

- How do different academic disciplines work with implementing the FAIR principles in research practice—for example in discipline-specific workflows, tools, etc., possibly drawing inspiration from or collaborating with international research environments?
- Which policies as well as motivational and supportive initiatives exist to support access to and reuse of research data, including the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital research objects (data, software, instruments, publications, etc.)?
- Describe best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for maintaining overall responsibility for data after researchers have left the institution and/or project funding has ended.

Members of working group A	
Name	Institution
Kirsten Krogh Kruuse (chair)	The Royal Danish Library
Bjørn Høj Jakobsen	University of Southern Denmark
Ding He	Technical University of Denmark
Hanne-Louise Kirkegaard	Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science
Jens Grønbech Hansen	Aarhus University
Jens Hybschmann	IT University of Copenhagen
Lars Ove Dragsted	University of Copenhagen
Kristoffer Gulmark Poulsen	Copenhagen Business School
Rene Belsø	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
Siri Volker	University of Copenhagen

Working group B – Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long-term preservation

The working group addresses initiatives requiring national coordination related to:

- What infrastructure is available for long-term preservation (10+ years) of research data of any kind at the national level, and how can coherence and collaboration be ensured between research institutions, DeiC, and the Danish National Archives?
- How can services for data management plans continue to be developed nationally and internationally, made machine-readable, and used in connection with reporting research data to the National Archives?
- Clarification of how research institutions work specifically with security infrastructure (Authentication, Authorization and Accounting Infrastructure, AAAI), especially for sensitive data, ensuring these can also be made FAIR.

Members of working group B	
Name	Institution
Bo Nygaard Bai (chair)	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
Asger Væring Larsen	The Royal Danish Library
Francesco Russo	Novo Nordisk Foundation
Hans Henrik Halvbjørn	Danish National Archives
Jonas Rank Møller	University of Copenhagen
Julian Quick	Technical University of Denmark
Kaare Aagaard	Aarhus University
Nicolaj Pedersen Tanderup	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
René Michelsen (Observer)	Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science

Working group C – financial plan for FAIR data

The working group addresses initiatives requiring national coordination related to:

- EU programmes (e.g., Horizon Europe) require applicants to prepare data management plans. To what extent can national research funders benefit from following this practice?
- How can it be ensured that research data and other electronic objects underlying published research results are preserved according to the FAIR principles after a project ends, with at minimum a Persistent Identifier (PID) and publicly accessible metadata, even when data are not openly available?
- Which data management costs can be included in budgets?

Members of working group C	
Name	Institution
Ulla Gro Nielsen (Chair)	Novo Nordisk Foundation
Børge Lindberg	Innovation Fund Denmark
Hanne-Louise Kirkegaard	Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science
Jakob D. Sørensen	Aarhus University
Lise Arleth	University of Copenhagen
Morten Andreasen	Danish National Research Foundation
Sandra Boerman	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
Tore Burkal Larsen	Independent Research Fund Denmark
Ole Kæseler Andersen	Aalborg University

Working group D – Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

The working group addresses initiatives requiring national coordination related to:

- Which competency profiles have research institutions defined for Data Stewardship research support functions? How have institutions built these functions?
- To what extent is there interest in developing and offering research support functions jointly at a national level (e.g., through a centralized or decentralized national competence center)?
- Is there interest in coordinating educational offerings (not research support) nationally within FAIR research data management? Could a national collaboration focus on division of labour, specialization, and joint national course offerings—for example, via a competence center under DeiC?
- How are incentive structures or merit systems currently used nationally or internationally to support FAIR data management practices?

Members of working group D	
Name	Institution
Mareike Buss (chair)	Copenhagen Business School
Claus D. Hansen	Aalborg University
Evgenios Vlachos	University of Southern Denmark
Falco Hüser	The Royal Danish Library
Haakon Lund	University of Copenhagen
Hannah Mihai	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
Sara Marie Westh	Aarhus University
Sacha Zurcher	Roskilde University

Working group E – Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration

The working group addresses initiatives requiring national coordination related to:

- Which security requirements should apply when sharing data?
- Given research groups' need to work nationally and internationally with sensitive data—which requires strong and flexible governance—what national and international solutions/services can support this need?
- Can a better understanding of the spectrum of data sensitivity be developed (not only personal data sensitivity, but also agreements, dual-use preprint, IPR, and researchers' own criteria)

Members of working group E	
Name	Institution
Thomas Schlichting (chair)	University of Copenhagen
Jakob Bech Petersen	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
Janni Lee Brodersen	University of Southern Denmark
Lasse Tougaard Friis	Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science
Mads Sinkjær Kjærgaard	Roskilde University
Morten Als Pedersen	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
Michael Collin	Aalborg University
Peter Severin de Fønss	Aarhus University

Working group F – Valuation of data

The working group addresses initiatives requiring national coordination related to:

- What criteria for the value (curation) of data and economic models are applied by local, national, and international data storage services to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

Members of working group F	
Name	Institution
Per Møldrup-Dalum (chair)	Aarhus University
Anne Sofie Fink Kjeldgaard	DeiC – Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
Carina Ollerup Christensen	Aalborg University
Michael Svendsen	The Royal Danish Library
Cecilie Maria Lindberg Laursen	Danish National Archives
Susanne den Boer Beckers	University of Copenhagen
Søren Friis Hansen	Copenhagen Business School